

Role of Political Skills for Organizational Engagement & Constructive Behavior Authors Details

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 08 , 2022</p> <p>Accepted: March 11, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Political Skills, organizational, Study Employs</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7719430</p>	<p><i>Political skill is one of the most important yet less researched topics in literature however it has gained its due attention now. The present research tests the role of political skill as a vital variable of organizational engagement and constructive behavior. The current study hypothesized 3 questions intended to find impact of political skill on employee engagement, how constructive behavior of employees influences by the political skills in the organization and what is the impact of political skills on employee satisfaction and loyalty in the organization. The study used Saunders' research onion research technique. This study employs a descriptive research strategy. 50 to 60 workers from all throughout the United States took part in our study as research study participants. A survey throughout the United States was collected the data needed for the study. SAS software program was used to analyze the data (Statistical Analytics Software). Results of the study indicated that a significant relation exists between political skill and organizational engagement which also impacts the constructive behavior.</i></p>

Introduction

Political Skills

"Political arenas" as defined by Mintzberg (1985) are a harsh reality for organizations that seek long-term and short-term self-interest optimization (Nawaz, Syed, & Dharejo, 2019). As a result of its poor reputation among employees, it is seen as a danger to the effectiveness and efficiency of businesses. Politics in the workplace has been shown to have a negative impact on a variety of work outcomes in previous studies (Mena et al., 2010).

Upwards of two decades ago, the concept of "political skill" was established as an essential attribute to have in order to be successful in the workplace (Ng, Hsu, & Parker, 2021; Sun et al., 2021). Employees require political talent, according to Pfeffer (2018), who's one of the first scholars to use the word in the academic literature. Organizations, according to Mintzberg (2019), are political arenas, necessitating the use of political acumen if they are to thrive. "The capacity to successfully comprehend people at work and to utilize such information to influence others in ways that advance one's personal and/or organizational goals" was described by Ferris et al. (2007) as political skill (Jordan et al., 2021). They also identified four crucial qualities of political skill: socially savvy, relationship quality, networking ability, and the appearance of sincerity as the four most important characteristics (Jordan et al., 2021).

To put it another way, organizations in Asian countries may be considered as a game arena of power, whereby people confront a limited supply of resources to pursue their own interests in a variety of ways (Fong, Tims, Khapova, & Beijer, 2021). When it comes to becoming a successful employee and dealing with political reality of businesses, political competence is considered crucial. Because we are interested in finding out how political talent affects a person's behavioral proclivities, we are going to study how political skill influences employee voice (Fong et al., 2021; Jordan et al., 2021; Srivastava & Madan, 2020).

For even more than three decades, management literature has held that politics are pervasive but detrimental to most people, teams, and organizations (Islam, Rashi, Nawaz, & Amer, 2020).

Pejorative views of politics portray it as a zero-sum game where personal interests are followed at the cost of others, resulting in backroom trade-offs, innuendos, and disloyalty. Researchers and managers alike are either avoiding or concealing the use of these tools, or making them the target of blame when adverse results occur (Islam et al., 2020). The research has proven favorable results such as improved productivity, career promotion, increased innovation, and decision-making consensus, which are worthy of further inquiry (Srivastava & Madan, 2020).

The term "political behavior" refers to "deliberate actions from a wide repertory which includes influence strategies, self-presentation, brand consciousness, voice and helpful behavior to govern such as creating, maintaining, modifying or abandoning the common meanings of organizational circumstances in order to accomplish desired results that would otherwise be impracticable. Employees and supervisors' efforts to attain personal and/or organizational objectives might have both self-serving and altruistic intentions, therefore a wide

definition is necessary (Ng et al., 2021). In order to achieve their objectives, workers and managers must function in a framework where they may be both active and passive participants. A micro- or macro-perspective on politics in organizations is possible (Ng et al., 2021).

Politics skills are described as "the capacity to successfully comprehend people in the workplace and to utilize such information in order to encourage other individuals or groups to behave in a manner that enhances one's personal and/or organizational goals. Contrary to popular belief, it is not a clone of concepts such as social intelligence, social competence, or self-monitoring (Fuller, Marler, & Hester, 2006). As a complex construct, political skill focuses on a person's capacity to comprehend people for their own advantage, which may be used in the workplace. The other components of social effectiveness, on the other hand, are more generic in nature and emphasize the development of interpersonal relationships (Fuller et al., 2006).

Political skill may be used in a variety of contexts, not only in "face-to-face" discussions. Several communication forms, like electronic mail or voice mail, have been bolstered by technological advancements (Gallagher, Porter, & Gallagher, 2019). Communication through technological methods, such as speech and tone of voice, and textual communication, may be conveyed in a convincing way by those with high levels of political ability. We're not only talking about the capacity to exhibit certain behaviors that are thought to be helpful in interpersonal relationships here. Political talent, on the other hand, enables individuals to generate synergy between discrete actions that surpasses the mere sum of the parts to actualize a set of relationship communication and successful execution which results in success in the workplace (Gallagher et al., 2019).

Study on political skill has mostly concentrated on the nomological net that surrounds it, with an emphasis on its own antecedents and effects, such that it serves as a mediator between political skill and significant organizational outcomes, such as work performance, tenure, and stress.. In general, the results show that political skill has a beneficial influence on these predictor variable, particularly on task performance (Michaelis, Rogbeer, Schweizer, & Özleblebici, 2021). Because of this, a meta-analysis on political skill is needed given the wide range of data on the link between performance and political ability. Political skill's ability to accurately predict work performance may be constrained by two factors: the kind of performance being assessed as well as the social context in which employees conduct their duties (Naveel et al., 2022; Yeboah-Ofori & Islam, 2019).

When it comes to political acumen, there is no one quality or ability. Instead, it represents a synergistic social dynamic that defies exact explanation, a collection of talents and abilities that are internally consistent, mutually reinforcing, and compatible (Gallagher et al., 2019). A style-type component matches what we mean when we say "political skills," and that's why we're calling it that. (1) "a method or form of expression in language; a means of putting ideas into words," or (2) "a particular and characteristic manner of presentation, execution, building or design in the art, period, work or occupation of any kind." In addition, we think that political talent may be learned or sculpted, but we also feel that it is inherent in a person to some level (Templer, 2018). The authors may seem to be hedging or attempting to have it both ways by saying this. While trait-versus-situation approaches to behavior were formerly considered mutually incompatible, the combination of dispositional and situational views on behavior indicates a more current understanding. Accordingly, we argue that a person's political acumen may be innate, but that it may never be fully developed if the necessary stimuli or precipitants are not provided (Bentley, Treadway, Williams, Gazdag, & Yang, 2017; Munyon et al., 2021; Templer, 2018). For political talent to be really successful, it must be able to adapt one's conduct to the intricacies and environmental needs of a given context. As with general mental capacity or intelligence, political skill adds to behavioral flexibility, which is critical in today's changing corporate situations (Bentley et al., 2017). Although cognitive flexibility is less susceptible to training, we believe that both forms of flexibility are crucial to effectiveness. When it comes to management development programs and hiring and promotion choices, we concentrate on the development of political skill as a possible new area of interest (Karatepe, Kim, & Lee, 2019; Williams, Brandon, Hayek, Haden, & Atinc, 2017).

According to Ferris et al. (2017), political competence is a talent that can be taught to people by providing them with training, mentorship, and socialization opportunities. Additionally, it's thought to be a result of a person's unique set of traits and experiences. Past research shows that the majority of studies in this area focused on the connections between political skills and consequences like job satisfaction, organizational commitment, confidence in one's abilities, success in one's professional career, devotion to one's employer's mission, and productivity at work (Ng et al., 2021).

Many crucial problems remain unsolved and need extensive theoretical and empirical attention, even while researchers have supplied some explanations to how politics are seen, enacted, and accountable for detrimental impacts such as with little debate on their beneficial influences. In other words, how do managers' differing views on politics in the workplace influence their political activity, and what personal, social, and situational aspects decide whether politics has a good or bad impact on teams or organizations? From a theoretical and practical multi-disciplinary perspective, the goal of this special issue is to stimulate a healthy conversation about the good and bad consequences of politics in the workplace.

There is no empirical evidence to support the theory that organizational politics may lead to favorable results. Workers' degrees of commitment might vary widely depending on the kind of workplace politics and support they experience (Landells & Albrecht, 2017; Malik et al., 2019).

An alignment of the challenge-stressor paradigm with the organizational support theory suggests that individuals in highly political and supportive companies may see their work environment as demanding. Because of the high degree of organizational politics, employees in these organizations will feel obligated to repay the organization for the assistance they get. Employees who work in low-politics and high-support situations are more likely to be engaged, but they will not be challenged by politics or inhibited by the workplace. The more people feel supported, the more likely they are to participate. As a result, they will have a lower level of involvement compared to those in deeply politicized and supportive situations, but a greater level of engagement compared to those in deeply politicized and unsupportive environments (Afzal, Afzal, & Naveel, 2021; Malik et al., 2019).

Organizational Engagement

A more accessible, "social organization," where leadership is expected to be in touch with what is going on and employees are demanding more "face time" where they can communicate directly with each other in teams, as well as with those who need decisions and action, is indeed on the rise, according to the authors (Hermans & Prins, 2020; Ouyang, Liu, & Gui, 2021; Suyono, Sawitri, Sunaryo, Mansur, & Risgiyanti, 2020)." The importance of social and political skills in the workplace is rising as a result of the growing level of interpersonal engagement (Mehralian, Peikanpour, Rangchian, & Aghakhani, 2020).

The concept of social effectiveness in the workplace has just emerged. Researchers are particularly interested in political skill, which refers to a person's capacity to affect or influence circumstances. According to Douglas (2002), the capacity to develop, manage and govern relationships successfully is referred to as "social effectiveness." Recent years have seen an increase in the prominence of social effectiveness dimensions, particularly political skill, among organizational psychology experts and academics (Kapoutsis, Papalexandris, Nikolopoulos, Hochwarter, & Ferris, 2011).

Any meaningful interaction between coworkers, particularly in the workplace, relies on social effectiveness to function well. The workplace's behavioral and emotional responses are influenced by the social effectiveness constructs (Hussain et al., 2018). Personality characteristics that focus on the ability to interact effectively with others are referred to as interpersonal personality variables. In the last twenty-five years, important contributions have been made to the defining and implementation of social effectiveness notions. The quantitative literature on organizational sciences has lately emphasized the role of political competence (Hussain et al., 2018).

Engagement is considered as comprehensive consequences and allegations for organizational outcomes and employee's performance. If engagement is successfully managed, the commitment of employees towards their organization will be more strengthened with the help of an engaging environment. Moreover, it can inspire the employees to go in-depth to provide work-related outcomes. For achieving competitiveness and innovation and to gain organizational effectiveness, employee engagement is considered a crucial factor. Employee engagement refers to an individual's satisfaction with, involvement with and enthusiasm for the task and job they do (Chandani, Mehta, Mall, & Khokhar, 2016). Engaged employees are the major factors that assist the organization in achieving overall organizational goals. Whereas, on the other hand, disengaged employees refers to trench the company financially by responding towards others with blame, resistance, distrust and indicating a low level of commitment (Chandani et al., 2016; Mishra & Kodwani, 2019).

An employee's emotional, cognitive, and physical energy is invested in their job when they are engaged in their employment. When employees think they can express themselves preferred self and psychologically connect with the task, they are more likely to be engaged in their jobs. The psychological qualities of meaningfulness, accessibility, and safety lead to employee engagement. Workers who have a sense of belonging and purpose at work are happier and more productive. The term "psychological availability" refers to workers' assumption that they have what resources necessary to finish their task and are free of non-work-related distractions. Last but not least, workers feel comfortable at their work when they think their actions won't have a negative impact on their position or career. Those who meet one or both of these psychological criteria may participate in their professional roles. Involved workers have a positive impact on businesses in a variety of ways. They are dedicated to their jobs and to the company, which makes them productive. They also exhibit behaviors associated with good corporate citizenship (Landells & Albrecht, 2017).

Challenge and hindrance stresses have been shown to have predictable effects on engagement. As an example, challenges in the workplace, such more responsibility and time constraints, are favorably connected with involvement, whereas hindrance stresses like bureaucracy, friction, overload and politics are adversely associated with it. Engagement is also positively correlated with the use of organizational assistance as a work resource.

A lack of involvement has been linked to an organization's politics, although other studies demonstrate that political perceptions may also be linked to high levels of engagement. There is an interesting correlation between the level of engagement of workers in highly politicized contexts compared to the level of engagement

of employees in less politicized environments. There seems to be a strong correlation between the amount of employee involvement and the level of political turbulence inside a firm.

It has been identified that comparatively little research has been done on political skills on organizational engagement and constructive behavior.

Constructive Behavior

According to its initial presentation, the word “constructive” was meant to indicate good and “organizationally functional” behaviors. If people are prepared to accept responsibility for their activities, it appears probable that they feel that their actions are acceptable since they were meant to be good to others, such as justifiable. A 'prosocial' behavior is one that is purposefully beneficial and focused on the well-being of others. Problem resolution, improvement ideas, process elimination, and the implementation of new, more effective work techniques all fall under the category of constructive behavior since they are designed to benefit the company as a whole. According to this view of 'constructive transformation,' behavioral components like voice behavior and taking leadership are consistent (Thompson, Buch, & Kuvaas, 2017). 'Deviant' conduct, on the other hand, may be designed to help the organization even if it violates the norms and standards of the organization. Pro-social rule violation and facilitative resistance are examples of 'positive deviance' Positive deviance may also involve conduct intended towards one of the business's customers or society instead of benefitting the organization. This is vital to keep in mind. There are kinds of 'positive deviance' such as whistleblowers or principled organisational dissent that are mainly geared at benefiting super organizational interests' rather than the organisation itself. An alternative definition for "destructive" deviant conduct is that it is meant to damage the company or its stakeholders. For example, stealing and organizational deviance are examples of "destructive" activity. Therefore, we believe that FRCC's conduct will be constructive since it is largely focused on improving the organization's efficiency or effectiveness (Bentley et al., 2017).

Corporations are not only putting more pressure on their workers to work more, but they are also encouraging them to take greater individual responsibility in addressing problems and identifying chances for growth. Indeed, many suggest that personal ambition and proactive conduct are becoming more important for both competitiveness and economic success. To put it another way, under the "new job relationship," positive change-oriented conduct has evolved as an obligation. Seiling (2001), for example, asserts that 'putting the responsibility for change on each person' is the first step in dealing with crises in companies. As a result, allocating accountability does not always guarantee that employees will take responsibility for their actions or that they will feel accountable. In other words, a person's attitude that he or she is "personally bound" to bring about positive change is likely to lead to constructive change-oriented conduct (Fong et al., 2021; Wihler, Blickle, Ellen III, Hochwarter, & Ferris, 2017).

Job characteristics theory, the most often used theoretical framework for understanding felt responsibility inside the workplace, is unlikely to adequately explain a proactively psychological state like felt responsibility for positive change. ' For one, it's all about "working harder," rather than encouraging people to participate in a more proactive approach to their work. Since today's businesses need more flexibility and change, job characteristics model has been criticized for being too narrowly focused. The basic argument of work design, according to Parker (2020), needs to encompass a wider variety of job qualities, new circumstances that may impact the efficacy of these job features, a wider range of outcomes, and additional mechanisms that connect all of these aspects together. If theories of job characteristics are to be relevant in today's businesses, experts propose that theories must contain proactive personality, proactively motivation, and proactive action. Specifically, Proactive work design models that Parker (2020) have presented require more theoretical development and testing before they can be used in the workplace. We build on Parker and colleagues' revised models by emphasizing on the perceived responsibility for positive change and moving toward a theory that better guides the design of work in modern organizations (Butt, Nisar, Nadeem, & Baig, 2017; Wihler et al., 2017).

Considering the organization centric approach, the study investigates organizational engagement and constructive behavior with the opportunity to induce and encourage their political skills in the organization. According to the study of McCoy, Cummings and Davies (2009), it has been investigated that the interest in constructive behavior has increased with the increase of interest in the procedures and techniques during the past years which emphasize the development of dynamics and positive qualities that directly lead to extraordinary organizational and individual performance. Constructive behavior is the one that helps in the reduction of tension and assists in resolving the conflict up to a great extent and support the organization in the goal achievement. It has been claimed by Soriano (2008), that organizations are considered as a “political arena”. However, nearby politics is a harsh certainty of the organizations which aims at a short- and long-term maximization of self-interest. As per Ferris et al. (2007), political skills refer to the capability to efficiently understand another individual at the workplace and to utilize such knowledge to inspire and impact others to act in such a way that enhances the objective of an individual and organization (Arrowsmith & Parker, 2013; Kidron & Peretz, 2018).

The rationale of the Research

As per the study of Block (2016), it has been evaluated those political skills refer to as a noteworthy part of the workplace. It is a multifaceted concept that is considered appropriate to assess the relationship and interactions in the organisation and emphasis an individual's ability to understand and support others for self-benefit (Nurhayatia, Thoyib, & Noermijati, 2017). As per the study of Ferris et al. (2007), it has been assessed that political skills have always been perceived as a negative factor in the organization (Haider, Fatima, & de Pablos-Heredero, 2020). However, there is a little study that has been previously done regarding the positive impact of political skills in the organisation. Therefore, the current study will focus on the positive factors of political skills in the organisation. The role of political skills on the constructive behaviour of the employee will be taken into consideration. Moreover, further investigation will be taken regarding the role of political skills on organisational engagement (Butt et al., 2017).

Problem Statement

Researchers in the area of management have made an effort to pinpoint the most crucial characteristics and abilities of people who hold leadership positions in the company. Political skill has been characterized as being separate from other traditionally important management abilities and stated as a remarkable and obvious part of a manager's conduct that leads to success and good behaviors in early literature on managing skills (Haider et al., 2020).

It is widely accepted that a manager's political acumen may have a significant influence on a range of organizational outcomes. In spite of the fact that some data suggests a relationship between political ability and organizational citizenship, positive behaviors such as helpful behavior and compassion remain untapped and encourage additional research (DuBrin, 2013).

While political talent may help managers better understand and influence people, there is no evidence that political skill has an impact on knowledge. As a result, they are able to comprehend and appreciate the needs and values of others as well as share their own thoughts and ideas with others. Additionally, a manager's political expertise helps tie them to their position via the fit and link mechanisms. Managers are better able to build networks and work connections as a result of this, and it seems that managers are more closely linked to the tasks they do (Robbins, 2010).

Despite the fact that direct links between political skill as well as positive behaviors like helping, compassion, knowledge sharing, and job embedding have been studied, more research is needed to examine specific mediating variables. These include organizational self-esteem, relationship quality, and personal reputation. By fostering a feeling of purpose at work and preserving a favorable personal credibility in the eyes of employees, political competence is thought to promote interpersonal trust and boost managers' self-esteem. This suggests that assessing how political skill helps managers see how they may contribute to their company and find meaning in their job in the presence of certain mediators would be a smart option. Further research into self-esteem, trust among friends and family and personal reputation as mediating factors is thus required (Konakli, 2016).

Mintzberg (2019) & Doldor et al. (2013) believed "political will" to be a crucial part of political conduct, and they were right. This link between political talent and outcomes can only be better understood if the function of political intention as a moderator is studied. Kimura (2015) made this point in his research of the relationship between public skill and outcomes.

There is a dearth of study on the growing implications of political skill, particularly in emerging countries like Pakistan, even though it is an essential concept and empirical evidence is accessible. Research on political talent is scarce in Pakistan, where the concept is in its infancy. For example, Muzzafar (2011) looked at how political skill mediated the link between perceived organizational justice and work stress, desire to leave and emotional commitment and contextual effectiveness on employees in the public and private sectors.. It was shown that self-monitoring and three political skills, such as social savvy, network capacity and interpersonal influence, mediated the relationship between proactive personality traits and employee performance. No study on the association between positive behaviors and work embeddedness and political competence in Pakistan has been conducted.

Based on Munyoun et al. (2015)'s recommendations for further research into the role of political skill on prosocial behavior, compassion, knowledge sharing, and job involvement in the presence of stipulated mediators and moderator, the current study will fill in the knowledge gaps and provide recommendations for bank managers (Konakli, 2016).

Aim and objectives of the research

The political skills are considered as for the self-interest rather than the interest of the overall organization and employees. Therefore, the main aim of the research is *"to evaluate the role of political skills in the organizational engagement and constructive behaviour of employee"*. Depending upon the nature of study, and problem statement following objectives are formulated:

- To achieve the aim of the research, the study will include the following objectives:
- To determine the impact of political skills on employee engagement

- To evaluate the constructive behaviour of employees influenced by the political skills in the organisation
- To investigate the impact of political skills on employee satisfaction and loyalty in the organisation

Research Questions

Focusing on the aim of the research, the study will answer the following questions:

RQ1 What is the impact of political skills on employee engagement?

RQ2 How constructive behaviour of employees influences by the political skills in the organisation?

RQ3: What is the impact of political skills on employee satisfaction and loyalty in the organisation?

Research Significance

It has been identified by Jain and Ansari (2018), that organisational politics has become the inevitable and major part of the whole organisation generally influence every worker in the organization up to some extent. It has been experienced that generally negative behaviour has been developed in the organisation and towards their job when employee feel victimised by the organisational politics. This negative behaviour harms the job performance of the employees. Various responses to similar situations are demonstrated by the employees due to having different personality dimensions (Khodabandeh & Sattari Ardabili, 2015). The current study is to evaluate that what is the major part and character played by the employee's political skills in the organisation and how it influences the organisational engagement and constructive behaviour of the employee. Organisational politics is considered a threat to the efficiency and effectiveness of the organisation due to its negative impression on the mind of the individual who is working in the organisation. In the past, it has been examined by many researchers that organisational politics harm the different outcomes of the job. However, now the trends have been changed to a greater extent, as positive aspects of organisational politics have been addressed by many of the studies such as effective persuasion, conflict resolution, justice restoration etc. In today's world, the managers must be effective in the organisation, however, to survive in the political environment at the workplace, the managers must develop their skillsets accordingly to cope with the challenges and changes that occur in the organisation. These skillsets will also help the managers to turn weaknesses into strengths and threats into opportunities (Konakli, 2016).

Theoretical Development

Their Ferris et al. (2017) theory of political or social influence in organizations focuses on the functioning of the political skill construction and how it influences oneself, others, and organizational practices in manners that manage shared meaning. The anticipated action of political skill on the formation of personal resources and personal ambitions was characterized by Ferris and colleagues as an intrapsychic process that shapes one's sense of self. Persuasion and persuasion strategies and reactions, networking and coalition building activities, performance assessments, citizenship and helpful behaviors are all included in the concept of influence on others. Group-level processes were also affected by the intervention (Joo & Bennett III, 2018).

The study intended to enhance the Ferris et al. (2017) model to give a more nuanced viewpoint from which to analyze political skill's functioning and uncover gaps in our understanding. Because of this, we extrapolate and interpolate the Ferris et al. (2017) model to include additional outcomes and hypotheses about these outcomes in the study's extension of their framework such as consider specific expressions of specific work outcome classifications they mention in their model, like job attitudes).

Overall, we've thought about how political skill affects self-assessment, situational evaluation, reaction to situations and responses from others, as well as processes inside groups and organizations. Intrapsychic influences of political competence may be captured by self-assessments and scenario evaluations. Behavioural reactions influenced by political skill are included in the category of situational responses. Finally, multilevel behavioral processes in which the political skill of one person influences others or compositions are often subsumed by group and organizational dynamics (Ferris, Ellen III, McAllister, & Maher, 2019; Joo & Bennett III, 2018).

Many academics believe that organizations are essentially political spaces. The assumption is that although intellect and hard effort play a role in performance, effectiveness, and success, other elements such as social savvy, placement, and savvy also play a vital role. When Pfeffer (2017) was advocating for an organizational approach that was political in nature

political competence is necessary for success, and he has urged for more study into the concept. Using persuasion, manipulation and negotiation, Mintzberg (2011) defined political competence as the ability to exert influence (Ferris et al., 2019).

Many studies have explored organizational politics, but there has been a fundamental gap in the evaluation of influencers' political skills, which has left us unable to explain why influence attempts succeed. Theories have argued that only showing off an influence effort is enough to prove its efficacy. Even if one studies the specific influence strategies or political behaviors that represent the what of influence, it is not adequate to focus just on this. Political skill must be examined thoroughly in order to comprehend how influence works, which includes the selection and implementation of acceptable influence methods in different contexts. To fill this gap, Ferris et al. (2001) developed a six-item, unidimensional scale with adequate psychometric qualities for the aim of conducting early concept explorations of political skill measurement.

According to Ferris and colleagues (2015), political skill is "the capacity to successfully comprehend and influence people at work, using such information in a manner that enhances one's personal and/or organizational goals." (paraphrased) Thus, politically savvy persons are able to adapt their conduct to varied and changing demands in a way that seems honest, inspires support and confidence, as well as successfully influence and control the behaviors of others in a manner that appears sincere (Ferris et al., 2019)

Discussion

The present work highlights the importance of developing political competence by extending previous models and testing them in new contexts. The aim of this study was to establish correlations between results. It has been confirmed in the literature that there is a positive correlation between, PS and organizational engagement. Thus, this study responded to the call (Munyon et al., 2013) to investigate its impact on positive behavior. In this study, FP practitioners, a group not discussed in the FP documents, examined the impact of organizational characteristics in traditional organizations. This study presents a literature review. The relationship provides: (i) PS has a positive impact on organizational performance and (ii) positive behavior has a positive impact.

Results of the Study

The results of this study are consistent with previous research. The estimation of the relationship between PS and organizational structure showed a strong positive correlation. This has been confirmed in the literature (Kolodinsky et al., 2004) that revealed significant relationships. However, this new study in the literature helps researchers understand certain factors that influence relationship patterns.

Limitations of the study and guidelines for future research

Some of the limitations of this study are: First, this study was conducted in Pakistan and not all results are available; in the collected data. Therefore, there is the possibility of methodological bias; however, this is confirmed by appropriate tests to assess impartiality. Also, bias in general (Podsakov et al., 2012) is not a problem for meaningful research. More research is needed to examine themes and other variables. affecting relationships.

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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